

Nikola Stanković,
Asistent,
Pravni fakultet, Univerzitet u Beogradu,
Republika Srbija

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OSVRT NA (NE)ODGOVORNOST DECE VOJNIKA U ORUŽANOM SUKOBU

Rad analizira teorijski okvir kada je reč o odgovornosti dece kao učesnika u oružanom sukobu. Prvo je postavljen normativni okvir zaštite dece, a koji se potom stavlja u složeni kontekst oružanog sukoba. U navedenim okolnostima, rad iznosi nekoliko primera učestvovanja dece u različitim oružanim sukobima. Integralni deo rada je posvećen pitanju odgovornosti dece vojnika, kako u kontekstu opšteg sistema međunarodnog javnog prava, ali i kroz dva njegova podsistema – međunarodno humanitarno pravo i međunarodno krivično pravo. U tom smislu se neminovno otvara jedno od ključnih pitanja međunarodnog humanitarnog prava u pogledu statusa dece boraca i potencijalne revizije istog, ali i daleko problematičnijeg pitanja čitavog međunarodnog javnog prava – pitanja odgovornosti. Upravo su ovo dve ključne tačke kojima se autor bavi u zaključnim razmatranjima.

Ključne reči: dete, oružani sukob, status deteta borca, pravna zaštita deteta borca, humanitarno pravo.

Nikola Stanković, LL.M.,
Teaching Assistant,
Faculty of Law, University of Belgrade,
Republic of Serbia

REFLECTION ON THE (NON)LIABILITY OF CHILD SOLDIERS IN ARMED CONFLICT

The paper analyzes the theoretical framework regarding the responsibility of children as participants in armed conflicts. First, the normative framework for the protection of children is established, which is then placed within the complex context of armed conflicts. In this regard, the paper presents several examples of children's involvement in various armed conflicts. An integral part of the paper is dedicated to the issue of the responsibility of child soldiers, both within the general system of international public law and within its two subsystems: international humanitarian law and international criminal law. It inevitably raises one of the key international humanitarian law issues regarding the status of child combatants and the potential revision of provisions governing this subject matter, as well as the issue of responsibility as a far more problematic question of the entire international public law. In the concluding considerations, the author addresses these two key points.

Keywords: child, armed conflict, status of child combatant, legal protection of child combatants, international humanitarian law.